

SOCIAL MEDIA IN EDUCATION: ITS USE, BENEFITS AND OBSTACLES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514563>

Annotation. This article describes the use of social media in education and demonstrates the advantages and disadvantages of using social media in the academic environment. The majority of scholars consider social media as a helpful tool to apply in the learning/teaching process as it could help them reshape teaching ways by using innovative technological options. On the one hand, they appreciate social media as a useful tool owing to creating fast communication with students and teachers while it also offers easy content delivery. On the other hand, they convey cautions that social media might distract students, as well as, raise some obstacles to the learning procedure.

Key words: social media, educational tool, social media usage, tertiary education, applications/tools, social networking platforms, Facebook, Twitter

It is a common fact that social media is of great importance in most people's lives. It particularly has an impact on people's work, life, and study. Today, teachers and professors are integrating social media in the teaching and learning process as an educational tool to motivate their learners and contribute to their educational development. Briefly, social media is affecting how learner study and interact today.

Mc Cay and Peet and Quan Haase put forward the following definition: "Social media are web-based services that allow individuals, communities, and organizations, to collaborate, connect, interact, and build community by enabling them to create, co-create, modify, share, and engage with user-generated content that is easily accessible". Social media has entered into individuals' life in double-quick time, on the other hand, it is not precisely what platforms and tools are considered social media. Mc Cay and Peet and Quan Haase analyzed social media from a variety of academic literature and revealed three basic themes including what social media activities enabled, how it allows these activities, and what content it encompasses. Furthermore, in accord with the dictionary definition, social media is termed as applications and websites enabling users to create and share content, as well as, to join in social networking.

Social media allows people to keep in touch with classmates and their families. For example, some of them may use a variety of social media applications to network and find career possibilities, connect with people across the world with interests, and share their thoughts, feelings, and insights online. Furthermore, it has evolved into an invaluable tool not only for communication but in the field of education as well. Typically, students use social media to share and obtain instant immediate information, reviews, and resolutions to their concerns.

By developing social media and social networking platforms, the majority of scholars have commenced with studying social media usage in diverse fields, encompassing education. In accordance with Yaros, Facebook and Twitter can create a learning atmosphere positively. For this reason, learners engage the social media in the learning process and have more enthusiasm for the subject despite the content. Another scholar Joosten discovered that some social networking platforms, including Facebook, are preferable for learners as there is an opportunity to make a discussion with the whole classroom overlearning management systems and email communication. This way could supply a close connection between learners and the teachers. Falahah and Rosmala clarified that there are social media tools that could be applied to some tasks in the academic field. They are as follows: task assignment, class rescheduling, examination, material searching and sharing, task negotiation, and others. Social media is also defined as the way of interaction between students and teachers. Social media assisted students to connect with lectures more regularly and effortlessly. Hamid et al express that social media inspires collaborative study and rises interactions. On the other hand, they warned that the use of social media is not suitable for some scientific instructions to teach chemistry, biology, and others. Nonetheless, other studies examined the perspectives on social media usage in tertiary education.

Numerous studies prove that there are some benefits and demerits of social media in tertiary education, too. Although they can offer more advantages, social media has problematic issues in terms of distractions, privacy obstacles, poor time management, information overload, and others. For example, Manca and Ranieri identified the positive and negative sides of social media usage in tertiary education. On the positive side, social media gives instant connection among social media users. Therefore, teachers can easily enable their learners to use a wide range of social media tools to deliver the content both synchronously and asynchronously. Negatively, social media could have unwilling drawbacks, such as devotion to social media, needless information, and effortless

interruption. Sobaih et al outlined that although social media could serve as a productive instrument to teach and learn in an academic atmosphere, particular barriers, containing security and privacy matters, time commitment, loss of monitoring, ethical issues, and others could be controlled.

To recapitulate, social media usage has the benefits and obstacles that were mentioned above. The merits of social media in education are highlighted by many scholars including easy communication, and fast sharing of information whereas drawbacks comprise privacy and security matters, wasting span, and donating to the digital divide. It is also an undeniable fact that there are not sufficient conducted researchers in the sphere of using social media in education. Therefore, it undoubtedly requires additional research to be carried out.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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